

High Energy Limit of the Wigner Transform Without The WKB Approximation

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In (1) the high energy limit of the Wigner transform $W_1(p,x,n)$ is investigated for the quantum oscillator. The WKB semiclassical approximation is used and the high energy wavefunction approximated by: $1/\sqrt{p(x)} \{ \exp(i p(x) x) + \exp(-i p(x) x) \}$ leading to the result of delta ($\delta(p - \sqrt{2m(E - V(x))}$) where $p(x) = \sqrt{2m(E - V(x))}$, P, X are classical momentum and position and $E = PP/2m + kXX/2$ energy.

In this note, we first observe that the WKB approximation may be used for any potential $V(x)$ to find a similar result. We then focus on obtaining the result without using the WKB approximation, but instead utilize: $H(p,x) \star W_1(p,x,n) = E_n W_1(p,x,n)$ (from (2)) where $H(p,x)$ is the classical Hamiltonian, \star the Moyal star product involving $\exp(i\hbar/2 \text{ Operator})$ and $W(p,x,n)$ the Wigner function (as used in (2)). The main idea is that in the classical limit, $\hbar \rightarrow 0$ so $\exp(i\hbar/2 \text{ Operator}) \rightarrow 1$. Thus $H(p,x)W_1(p,x,n \rightarrow \text{large}) = E_n W_1(p,x,n \rightarrow \text{large})$. In (2) it is shown that $\int dp dx W_1(p,x,n) = 1$, so $\int H(p,x) W_1(p,x,n \rightarrow \text{large}) = E$. As a result, $W_1(p,x,n \rightarrow \text{large})$ acts as a delta function enforcing $pp/2m + V(x) = E$.

Wigner Transform

The Wigner transform $W_1(x,p,n)$ takes a quantum wavefunction (for a specific energy level n) and converts it into a function of p,x such that:

$$\int dp W_1(x,p,n) = a_n^*(p)a_n(p) \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{and} \quad \int dx W_1(x,p) = W_n^*(x)W_n(x) \quad ((1b))$$

Where $a_n(p)$ is the momentum wavefunction and $W_n(x)$ the spatial one. The Wigner transform is defined as:

$$W_1(x,p,n) = \int ds / (2\pi\hbar) W_n^*(x-s/2) \exp(-ips/\hbar) W_n(x+s/2) \quad ((2))$$

The Wigner transform is sometimes negative in value and so cannot fully represent a classical probability. We note that it pertains to a specific quantum energy level. It is possible to smooth over $W_1(x,p,n)$ with a Gaussian to obtain a Husimi distribution in (x,p) and to also create a coherent state in (x,p) which is linked to a statistical mechanical weight which considers all energy levels. Here we only consider $W_1(x,p,n)$ for a specific n quantum energy level and ask what happens to $W_1(x,p,n)$ in the high n limit.

Wigner Transform and the WKB Approximation

A simple WKB approach (from (3)) assigns the wavefunction in the high energy level limit as:

$$W(x) \text{ proportional to: } \exp(i p(x) x) \quad \text{where } p(x) = \sqrt{2m(E - V(x))} \quad ((3))$$

In (1) a more involved WKB wavefunction is used, but as a first test of the high n limit we use ((3)). Then ((2)) becomes:

$$W_1(x, p, n \rightarrow \text{very large}) = (2 \cdot 3.14 \cdot \hbar) \int ds \exp(-i(p-p(x))) \text{ or } (2 \cdot 3.14 \cdot \hbar) \int ds \exp(-i(p+p(x))) \quad ((4))$$

$$\text{This equals: } 1/\hbar \delta(p-p(x)) + 1/\hbar \delta(p+p(x)) \quad ((5))$$

Thus the Wigner transform appears to be a distribution which in the high energy limit enforces the constraint that $pp/2m + V(x) = E$ which is a compact way of considering motion to the right and left together.

One may note that for any energy level n , the quantum time-independent Schrodinger equation may be written as:

$$p_{rms}(x) p_{rms}(x) / 2m + V(x) = E_n \quad ((6a)) \quad \text{where } p_{rms}(x) = \sqrt{-2m d/dx dW/dx} \quad ((6b))$$

$$\text{At the same time: } W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((7))$$

Thus, there is one $p_{rms}(x)$ (at any n), but many possible p values at a given x . In the high n limit, p becomes equivalent to $p(x)$ the classical result according to ((5)), but this means that p is semiclassical i.e. is changing in x . For low n , there is a range of p 's and the best one can say is that $p_{rms}(x)$ is the root mean square average. One cannot favour a single p as in the high energy limit.

Harmonic Oscillator and (1)

In (1) a study of the Wigner transform of the quantum oscillator is made with a special focus on the high n limit. The Wigner transform for a full oscillator n level wavefunction is calculated and in the high n limit it is stated that the "Wigner function does not have a clear classical limit". The next step in (1) is to use the WKB semiclassical approximation for the wavefunction. A more complicated form than ((3)) is used, namely:

$$W(x) \text{ (WKB)} = A/\sqrt{p(x)} \sin(1/\hbar S(x) + u) \quad ((8a))$$

Where $A = \sqrt{4m/T}$ where $T = 2 \cdot 3.14 / \omega$, $p(x) = \sqrt{2m(E - .5kx^2)}$, and $S(x) = \int (0, x) p(y) dy$ and $u = .5$.

It is noted in (1) that ((8)) is very similar to the exact wavefunction except near the classical turning points.

The authors of (1) argue that the form ((8)) ultimately leads to:

$$\text{Constant } \int ds \exp(-ips/\hbar) \{ \exp(i p(x)s/\hbar) + \exp(-i p(x) s/\hbar) \} \quad ((8b))$$

One may note that the term in $\{ \}$ in ((8b)) represents quantum interference, but with the combination of $\exp(ips/\hbar)$ (factor in front of $\{ \}$) one obtains two delta functions showing that motion may either be to the right or to the left with no interference between the two.

$$W_1(p,x,n \rightarrow \text{very large}) = m/(T p(x)) \{ \delta(p-p(x)) + \delta(p+p(x)) \} \quad ((9a))$$

This is ultimately a delta function $(pp/2m + V(x) - E)$ using a property of delta functions from (4):

$$\delta(x-a) = 1/(2|a|) \{ \delta(x-a) + \delta(x+a) \} \quad ((9b))$$

High n Limit of the Wigner Function without the WKB Wavefunction

We suggest that one may find the high energy level behaviour of the Wigner transform without using the WKB approximation. We use instead the relationship from (2):

$$H(p,x) ** W_1(p,x,n) = E_n W_1(p,x,n) \quad ((10)) \quad \text{where } H(p,x) \text{ is the classical Hamiltonian}$$

** is the Moyal star product defined as:

$$f(p,x) ** g(p,x) = f(p,x) \exp(-i\hbar/2 \{ d/dx \text{ left } d/dp \text{ right} - d/dp \text{ left } d/dx \text{ right} \}) g(p,x) \quad ((11))$$

We argue that in the high n limit, $\hbar \rightarrow 0$ ((12)). Thus ((10)) becomes:

$$H(p,x)W_1(p,x,n \rightarrow \text{very large}) = E_n W_1(p,x,n \rightarrow \text{very large}) \quad ((12))$$

In (2) it is shown that $\int dp dx W_1(p,x,n) = 1$. Thus:

$$\int dx dp H(p,x) W_1(p,x,n \rightarrow \text{very large}) = E_n \quad ((13))$$

As a result:

$$W_1(p,x,n \rightarrow \text{very large}) \text{ essentially acts as a delta function enforcing } pp/2m + V(x)=E. \quad ((14))$$

One does not need to make use of the WKB wavefunction.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that the Wigner transform $W_1(p,x,n)$ for a specific energy level n quantum wavefunction has been shown to lead to a delta function in the high n limit for an oscillator in (1) using the WKB approximation. We argue that the WKB approximation yields this result for any $V(x)$. We also argue that one does not need to use the WKB wavefunction

approximation, but rather may use the classical limit of the Moyal star product \star from (2) i.e. $H(p,x) \star W_1(p,x,n) = E W_1(p,x,n)$ where $H(p,x)$ is the classical Hamiltonian. In the high n limit, i.e. classical limit, $\hbar \rightarrow 0$ so $\star \rightarrow 1$. Thus $H(p,x) W_1(p,x,n \rightarrow \text{very large}) = E W_1(p,x,n \rightarrow \text{very large})$. The integral of W_1 is 1 so $W_1(p,x,n \rightarrow \text{very large})$ must act like a delta function enforcing $pp/2m + V(x) = E$.

References

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